

1 **Human trafficking in medical oncology.**

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6 Human trafficking is defined in the Trafficking Victims Protection Act of 2000 as “the recruitment,
7 harboring, transporting, supplying, or obtaining a person for labor or services through the use of force,
8 fraud, or coercion”. Hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) together with non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC)
9 cancer of the liver and the lung, result in over 2 million deaths per year world-wide. We introduce here the
10 concept of cancer as a source of global human trafficking, noting two solid tumor types, HCV and NSCLC
11 that manifest massive burdens in human life (mortality) associated with cancer death. The specific global
12 trafficking of humans resulting from cancer diagnoses en masse in the community features medical
13 transactions and entities that are among the most costly socioeconomic interactions industry-wide (i.e.,
14 medicine, healthcare, state-sponsored medical programs, insurance and the economy), and an industry
15 engaged in the sale of products, medicines and medical research goods among whose basic and major
16 purposes or aims is to provide usable medicines and serve hospitalization needs for patients with cancer.

17 Citations

18 1. Logan, T.K., Walker, R. and Hunt, G., 2009. Understanding human trafficking in the United States.
19 *Trauma, Violence, & Abuse*, 10(1), pp.3-30.
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